

Scientific questions which support the DSO in the selection and development of the Local Flexibility Market platform

Gábor Mihály PÉTER ^{1*}, István TÁCZI ², Bálint HARTMANN ²

¹ E.ON Észak-dunántúli Áramhálózati Zrt., Hungary

²Department of Electric Power Engineering, Budapest University of Technology and Economics, Hungary

* Correspondence: gabor.peter1@eon-hungaria.com

Abbreviations in the questions, which are explained below:

LFM: Local Flexibility Market

CM: Congestion Management

HV: High voltage

HV/MV: High voltage/ Medium voltage substation

MV: Medium voltage

LV: Low voltage

TSO: Transmission System Operator

DSO: Distribution System Operator

Balancing: TSO balancing market

DER: Distributed Energy Resources

BRP: Balancing Responsible Party

DAM: Day ahead Market

D-1: Day ahead

ID: Intraday

Questions to answer for LFM evaluation

1. To postpone traditional grid expansion until it is more economically viable? The alternative is network reinforcement.
2. Where does flexibility resolve congestion without conventional grid development?
3. How can local flexibility handle unexpected local load growth?
4. How does distributed renewable capacity affect on higher voltage level?
5. How can flexibility help for DSO during planned/unplanned incidents.
 - What is the difference between 1) and 2)?

- What is the difference between 1, 2, and 3?
 - What other network problems do you see that the local flexibility market could serve as a solution to or help solve?
6. Why is observability important? How is it related to controllability?
 7. Which physical parameters need to be controlled? (state variable, control variable, controlled variable).
 8. How does this differ from TSO Congestion Management (CM)?
 9. Voltage level considerations:
 - (1) What is the difference in forecasting load & production for HV, HV/MV and MV and/or LV networks? How does this affect forecasting challenges?
 - (2) How can TSO CM (Congestion Management) and Balancing objectives be aligned with DSO LFM considering voltage level difficulties?
 10. What is TSO CM Goal and How is it implemented?
 11. What is TSO Balancing Goal and How is it implemented?
 12. What BRP Portfolio Optimization Goal and How is it implemented?
 13. How can all of the above be related to and affect the DSO Local Flexibility Market?
 14. Who provides network flexibility?
 - (1) What does the DSO use, what can it use, and how?
 - (2) Why does the TSO use Local DERs (Distributed Energy Resources)?
 - (3) How does the TSO use flexibility services of DERs for Congestion Management (CM) and Balancing?
 - (4) How does BRP use DERs for portfolio optimization?
 15. Does the fact that both the TSO and BRP use DERs imply the existence of a Local Flexibility Market in which both TSO and BRP participate? Does this mean that both a TSO and a BRP can be a player in LFM, despite the fact that LFM is designed to solve DSO network problems? Or do you see other LFM platforms that solve not only DSO network problems?
 - (1) How can it be distinguished? How can LFM be defined from a participant and problem-solving perspective?
 - (2) Many platforms are called flexibility platforms just because TSOs & BRPs use DERs—what are the classification implications?
 16. Liquidity in DSO LFM
 - (1) How does competition for resources between DSO, TSO, and BRP affect liquidity?
 17. Real DSO LFM versus TSO CM:
 - (1) What are the connection points between DSO LFM and TSO CM?
 - (2) What are the differences from flexibility sources point of view?
 - (3) Does it make sense to compare them from flexibility sources point of view?

18. Real DSO LFM versus TSO Balancing:
 - (1) What are the connection points between DSO LFM and TSO Balancing?
 - (2) What are the differences from flexibility sources point of view?
 - (3) Does it make sense to compare them from flexibility sources point of view?
19. DSO LFM versus Electricity Wholesale Market:
 - (1) What are the connection points between DSO LFM and Electricity Wholesale Market?
 - (2) What are the differences from flexibility sources point of view?
 - (3) Does it make sense to compare them from flexibility sources point of view?
20. Does BRP portfolio optimization create a link between DSO LFM and Electricity Wholesale Market?
 - (1) Is there a connection because of the BRP portfolio? That is, when BRP optimizes its portfolio, can it use flexibility?
 - (2) Does imbalance correction play a role? How does this differ from portfolio optimization?
21. What determines the price of flexibility services in LFM?
 - i) Is DSO CAPEX vs. DAM price (opportunity cost) the determining factor?: That is, the traditional investment cost (CAPEX) of the DSO, which would solve the management of network bottlenecks, or could the Day-ahead exchange price of the electricity market be the decisive factor? Below are the two aspects:
 - (1) What are the Advantages from one (CAPEX) and the other (DAM price) perspective?
 - (2) What are the disadvantages from one (CAPEX) and the other (DAM price) perspective?
 - ii) How do the above affect the design and operation of the LFM platform? Which one can cause what problems for the DSO? Which one can be more advantageous when faced with an extensive network where multiple bottlenecks can develop separately?
22. What determines TSO Balancing prices?
23. What determines TSO CM prices?
24. What determines Wholesale BRP portfolio optimization prices?
25. How do price interactions affect LFM liquidity?
 - (1) How does TSO Balancing market pricing impact DSO LFM pricing?
 - (2) How does TSO CM pricing impact DSO LFM pricing?
 - (3) How does Electricity Wholesale market pricing affect DSO LFM pricing?

26. What can DSO use to predict bottlenecks, congestion, voltage problems, i.e. to predict network flexibility needs? What kind of forecast and calculation serves this purpose?
27. Related to the previous question, what are the challenges and difficulties?
28. What calculation methods, measurements, or hybrid approaches are common? What seems to be the most future-proof solution, and why?
29. What types of forecasting methods does TSO use?
 - (1) What makes it easier compared to DSOs?
 - (2) How does forecasting work for TSO CM & TSO Balancing? What are the challenges & advantages ?
30. What forecasting approach does BRP portfolio optimization use? What are the challenges & advantages ?
31. How does the forecasting issue impact market interactions, sequencing, and products if we are talking about the following markets: DSO Local Flexibility Market (LFM), TSO Balancing Market, Electricity Wholesale Market?
32. Where is baseline relevant in flexibility markets for the DSO?
 - (1) from network problem Forecasting perspective (forecast here covers network calculation as well, e.g. state estimation, load flow, etc.)
 - (2) from Settlement with flexibility service provider perspective
33. Where is baseline relevant for the TSO?
 - (1) Is Baseline in TSO CM Relevant for Forecast or Settlement?
 - (2) Is Baseline in TSO Balancing Relevant for Forecast or Settlement?
34. Why is the baseline relevant for BRP portfolio optimization? How is it calculated?
35. Where can the different baseline methodologies of the different markets mentioned above cause problems from the DSO Local Flexibility Market perspective?
36. What determines DSO LFM sequencing? How are markets coordinated in terms of Electricity Wholesale market, TSO Balancing, TSO CM, DSO Local Flexibility Market?
37. What does the result of the previous question above mean for DSOs?
38. What does the result of the previous question above mean for DSOs?
 - (1) Is there a difference between CM and Balancing?
 - (2) If yes, why?
 - (3) How does this affect DSOs?
39. What market sequence can be used for BRP portfolio optimization? How does this market sequencing impact DSO LFMs? How does this market sequence affect TSO Balancing & CM?
40. When must DSO LFMs consider other market sequences (TSO CM, Balancing, Wholesale)? How can dependencies be mapped on a scale from tight to fully independent constraints?
41. How does competition for DER flexibility sources impact DSO-TSO cooperation?

- (1) Where and for what purpose does the TSO use DERs?
 - (2) Where and for what purpose does the DSO use DERs?
 - (3) How does resource competition affect DSO liquidity?
 - (4) Is cooperation necessary due to flexibility resource allocation?
42. TSO's handling of unused DSO flexibility bids
- (1) What is the objective of bid transfers to the TSO?
 - (2) What structural and market approaches exist?
 - (3) What are the impacts of bid transfers on market complexity and structure?
43. Why must TSO's flexibility (Balancing, CM) usage be considered by DSOs?
- (1) Due to network effects? Should flexibility providers' grid connection procedures incorporate constraints instead?
 - (2) What if DSO LFM didn't exist? How were DSO constraints previously aligned with TSOs?
 - (3) Is DSO-TSO cooperation actually necessary?
44. Cross-market clearing and co-optimization
- (1) Is co-optimization across markets (TSO Balancing, TSO CM, Wholesale, DSO LFM) feasible?
 - (2) Why is co-optimization important?
 - (3) Does it introduce unnecessary complexity?
 - (4) Pros & cons of co-optimization
 - (5) Is co-optimization necessary because TSOs want access to DERs?
 - (6) How should DSO priority be considered in co-optimization?
 - (7) How does co-optimization impact market sequencing?
45. What does D-1 (Day-Ahead) market timing mean for LFMs?
- (1) Pros & Cons from forecasting & baseline perspectives
 - (2) Pros & Cons from market interaction perspective
 - (3) Should LFMs align with TSOs or the Wholesale Market?
 - (4) Impact on Flexibility Service Providers (FSPs) and uncertainty
46. What does ID (Intraday) market timing mean for LFMs?
- (1) Pros & Cons from forecasting & baseline perspectives
 - (2) Pros & Cons from market interaction perspective
 - (3) Should LFMs align with TSOs or the Wholesale Market?

- (4) Impact on FSPs and uncertainty
47. From a platform structure/complexity perspective, what is the difference between D-1 and ID in DSO LFM?:
 - (1) From Forecast & Baseline perspective
 - (2) From Platform hierarchy perspective
 - (3) From TSO cooperation mechanisms perspective
 - (4) From Wholesale Market & FSP interaction perspective
 48. What products exist in today's platforms/markets?
 - (1) In DSO LFM
 - (2) In TSO CM
 - (3) In TSO Balancing
 - (4) In Electricity Wholesale
 49. What electricity markets should be considered for LFM development?
 - (1) Market design & product compatibility considerations
 50. How do previous topics (Physical Background of DSO Local Flexibility Market, forecasting, baseline) impact product design?
 51. How does TSO-DSO cooperation influence product offerings? Are there mandatory product design constraints due to bid transfer from DSOs to TSOs? What products fit DSO needs, and how does that affect cooperation?
 52. What kind of bids exist in different markets (see previously defined), and what does their structure depend on?
 53. Product vs. Bid structure:
 - (1) How does bid structure impact product design?
 - (2) How are market & technical characteristics related to bids and products?
 54. How do different markets structure bids, and what are the influencing factors?
 - (1) Do bids manifest market features or technical requirements?
 - (2) How do bids and products reflect market structure and constraints?
 55. How do different regulatory frameworks impact LFM if we consider the following categories?
 - (1) Voluntary flexibility providers, market based service
 - (2) Non-firm contracts or flexible connection agreements
 - (3) Curtailment or Redispatch (non-market based or rule-based, but compensated flexibility)
 56. How does this affect platform complexity?

(1) Clearing complexity. What are the consequences of having to include two non-market-based services? The rule-based one probably doesn't enter the market because it doesn't want to provide it, and the bid has to be created instead.

(2) Flexibility registry complexity

(3) Execution risk, i.e. how does the given actor implement the flexibility requirement for the DSO, what is the probability of providing flexibility at all?

57. What auction types are possible in LFM's?

- Pros
- Cons

58. What optimization techniques are used in clearing?

- Pros
- Cons

59. What mathematical challenges arise in optimization?

- Impact on platform development
- What causes difficulties?